

Supplemental Information

in situ Tracking of Water Oxidation Generated Nanoscale Dynamics in Layered Double Hydroxides Nanosheets

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EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials. Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O and hexamethylenetetramine (HMT) were purchased from Alfa Aesar, KOH and formamide were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) were purchased from Fisher Scientific. Deionized water with a resistivity ≥ 18 M Ω was used to prepare all aqueous solutions.

Preparation of SL-NiCo LDHs NSs. In a typical hydrothermal procedure, 3 mL Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (0.5 M), 1 mL Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (0.5 M), 40 mL SDS (0.25 M) and 12 mL HMT (1 M) were dissolved in 44 mL deionized Milli-Q water to form a homogeneous solution. The mixture was sealed in a 200 mL Teflon vessel and heated at 120°C for 24 hours. The products were rinsed several times with water and ethanol and dried overnight to obtain the bulk NiCo LDHs (the characterization are shown in Figures S1-2). Next, 15 mg bulk NiCo LDHs were dispersed in 30 mL formamide and maintained at 40°C for 5 days. The suspension was centrifuged at 2,000 rpm for 30 min, followed by transfer of the supernatant to a clean tube and centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 30 min. Finally, the sediments were washed with water and ethanol several times and suspended in 2 mL of ethanol.

Preparation of WE. 30 μ L SL-NiCo LDHs nanosheet suspension was spin-coated on a freshly cleaved HOPG surface, and subsequently heated at 180°C for 60 min.

Preparation of PSL-NiCo LDHs NSs. The SL-NiCo LDHs NSs/HOPG were exposed to Ar plasma for 1 min in a plasma reactor (commercial 13.56 MHz RF source), with a power of 300 W and a pressure of 40 Pa.

Material Characterization. High-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADF-STEM) was performed using a 200 kV FEI Talos F200X analytical STEM equipped with a TWIN lens, and an X-FEG electron source. Scanning nanobeam electron diffraction (NBED) patterns of individual NSs were collected using a beam with a convergence angle of 0.6 mrad. The data was subsequently analyzed using non-negative matrix factorization (NMF). Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) data was collected on the same microscope using the ChemiSTEM/SuperX G1 setup. Data was analyzed and visualized using the HyperSpy package. X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD) was carried out on a Rigaku Smart Lab diffractometer, using a Cu source and a convergent beam mirror (Cu K α 1 radiation, $\lambda = 1.540593$ Å). The Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was measured with the Cary 630 FTIR spectrometer (Agilent) with the dTGS detector. Quantitative mechanical measurements were conducted using PeakForce Quantitative NanoMechanics (PF-QNM) Mode: the probe is calibrated according to the released notes from Bruker, the estimated tip radius is ~ 30 nm; the deflection sensitivity was calibrated to be 17.133 nm/V by a PF-QNM ramp on HOPG; the spring constant was calibrated to be 0.60082 N/m by thermal tuning; a Poisson's ratio of 0.5 was used here. The phase profile was acquired in tapping mode. The force curves at points of interest were collected using a "point and shoot" module in EC-ScanAsyst. All images were further processed and analyzed by SPIP or Nanoscope.

Electrochemical characterization. The classical electrochemical measurements were performed in a homemade cell (the electrode exposed area is 0.56 cm²) with a three-electrode system using an electrochemical workstation (CHI 760E). The sample prepared on HOPG was used as WE, and a carbon rod and a Hg/HgO electrode were used as CE and RE, respectively.

Computational method. All DFT calculations employed the Vienna Ab initio Simulation Package (VASP) together with the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) exchange-correlation functional.¹⁻³ To generate an accurate adsorption geometry, the van der Waals (vdW) interactions were considered using Grimme's semiempirical DFT+D3 scheme.⁴ The Hubbard-U correction was used to describe the local d-electrons of Ni and Co in SL-NiCo LDHs. The U-J values of Ni and Co are 3.8 and 4.0 eV, respectively. A cutoff energy of 450 eV was set in all calculations. For structural optimizations, the used Brillouin zone sampling was (9×9×1) for the (001) surface and (5×1×1) for (110) surface of SL-NiCo LDHs⁵. The convergence criterion of energy difference was set to 10⁻⁴ eV for structural optimization, and 10⁻⁵ eV for static calculations. The atomic positions were relaxed until the maximal force on each atom was smaller than 0.02 eV/Å. The following mechanism for OER was adopted:

The * indicates the active site in SL-NiCo LDHs, and *OH, *O, *OOH are the intermediate species on the active sites. The Gibbs free energies of each step are calculated by the following formula:

$$\Delta G_1 = E_{*OH} + 1/2E_{\text{H}_2} - E_* - E_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + \Delta ZPE - T\Delta S \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta G_2 = E_{*O} + 1/2E_{\text{H}_2} - E_{*OH} + \Delta ZPE - T\Delta S \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta G_3 = E_{*OOH} + 1/2E_{\text{H}_2} - E_{*O} - E_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + \Delta ZPE - T\Delta S \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta G_4 = 4.92 - \Delta G_1 - \Delta G_2 - \Delta G_3 \quad (8)$$

E_* , E_{*OH} , E_{*O} , E_{*OOH} , represent the total energy of intermediate species and E_{H_2} , $E_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ indicate the total energy of H₂ and H₂O. The electrocatalytic activity at a finite temperature was considered by introducing the correction of Zero-Point Energy (ZPE) and entropy change.⁶

FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure S1. (a) XRD pattern of bulk NiCo LDHs precursor (DS-NiCo LDHs). The diffraction peaks at about 14° and 33° correspond to the (003) and (101) planes of the α -Ni(OH)₂ (JCPDS 38-0715). The peak at 8° is attributed to the extended basal spacing induced by the intercalation of dodecyl sulfate (DS) ions.⁷ (b) FTIR of NiCo LDHs. The stretching mode of sulfate (-OSO₃⁻) in DS ions contributes to the peaks in the range of 1300-900 cm⁻¹.

Figure S2. Spatial elemental distributions of SL-NiCo LDHs NSs.

Figure S3. Conductive AFM measurement. (a) AFM image and (b) I-V curves obtained by point shoot on LDHs (orange) and HOPG (black). The typical I-V characteristic curves (obtained on multi-layers NiCo LDHs) reveal conductive features, indicating sufficient electrical contact between the LDHs and HOPG substrate. It is reasonable to conclude that the SL-NiCo LDHs NSs show sufficient electrical contact with HOPG.

Figure S4. (a, b) AFM topography images of SL-NiCo LDHs NSs. Scale bar, 1 μm . Color scale, -2~8 nm. (c) Corresponding size statistics distribution.

Figure S5. (a) AFM image and (b) CV curves obtained on HOPG in 0.1M KOH.

Figure S6. (a) Scanning electrochemical cell microscopy (SECCM) and CV curves obtained on 5 points of SL-NiCo LDHs NSs/HOPG electrode in 0.1M KOH.

Figure S7. (a) The detailed voltage steps for *in situ* EC-AFM measurements, and (b) simultaneously recorded current density. The voltage step begins at 300 mV, then progressively steps to 700 mV, and finally regresses to 300 mV.

Figure S8. *in situ* AFM images at the above voltage steps. The applied voltage is displayed in the upper left corner of each image. Scale bar, 500 nm. Color scale, -1~4 nm. AFM images were captured at each voltage step with an acquisition time of 567 s. We capture two images at anodically 400 mV and 650 mV.

Figure S9. *in situ* AFM images of the single NS obtained at anodically stepping of (a) 400 mV, (b) 650 mV, (c) backward stepping of 650 mV, under successive switching of the voltage to (d) 700 mV (700 mV-O₂) and (e) 300 mV (300 mV-R₂).

Figure S10. High-resolution lateral force image (left) and the corresponding zoom in low pass-filtered image (right) of (a) SL-NiCo LDHs NSs and (b) after chronopotentiometry measurement at 650 mV for 15 min. Silicon cantilevers (PNP-DB-20 with a spring constant ≈ 0.27 N/m, Olympus) were employed for the measurements under the normal load of 2 nN.

Table S1. Detailed statistics for the lattice parameters of the as-prepared NiCo LDHs and the active phase were obtained by selecting a few regions from the high-resolution lateral force images from Supplementary Figure S10.

Sample	selected region	a/nm	b/nm	area of unite cell after correction/nm ²	average area/nm ²	surface strain/nm ²
As-prepared phase	1	0.269	0.242	0.0627	0.0633	25.1%
	2	0.271	0.237	0.0631		
	3	0.262	0.228	0.0595		
	4	0.281	0.254	0.0679		
Active phase	1	0.235	0.174	0.04783	0.0474	
	2	0.225	0.237	0.048		
	3	0.23	0.233	0.0458		
	4	0.228	0.236	0.048		

Figure S11. *in situ* AFM images at (a, c) OCV and (b, d) 700 mV. The selected nanosheets for counting the distribution of surface strain are highlighted by dashed polygons. The scale bars for a and c are 500 nm and 100 nm, respectively.

Figure S12. HAADF-STEM images of SL-NiCo LDHs NSs with intrinsic line defects, as indicated by the white arrows. In general, a large nanosheet is prone to generating defects during the exfoliation process.

Figure S13. Schematic illustration of the edge site and basal plane site of NiCo LDHs.

Figure S14. The optimized structure for all intermediates adsorbed on O site on the (110) surface of NiCo LDHs under a 16 Å vacuum, dashed lines present partial vacuum.

Figure S15. The optimized structure for all intermediates adsorbed on Ni site on the (001) surface of NiCo LDHs under a 16 Å vacuum.

Figure S16. AFM images obtained (a) before and (b) after performing 30 CVs. Scale bar, 100 nm. Color scale, 0~3 nm. The white arrows highlight the hairlines produced in the nanosheet.

Figure S17. Height profiles along the cross-section of the AFM images in Figure 2a clearly demonstrate the height changes of the same region.

Figure S18. (a) *in situ* AFM image of SL-NiCo LDHs NSs at 600 mV. Color bar, -4~4 nm. Scale bar, 300 nm. (b) Height profile of the micropancake along the white line in a.

Nanobubble formation occurs through the accumulation of oxygen gas as OER processes, followed by nucleation and growth stages.⁸⁻¹⁰ This process involves a dynamic equilibrium between the creation of gas molecules during OER and their loss through diffusion into the electrolyte, and they can dissolve into the electrolyte upon the application of reducing voltage.^{11,12} Micropancake formation is a result of the accumulation of diffused oxygen gas on the HOPG electrode,

followed by nucleation and growth. HOPG exhibits a different nucleation mechanism compared to LDHs due to its hydrophobic nature. The electrode-gas attraction is significantly stronger than the electrode-water attraction, which enables the nucleation of gases in the form of micropancakes.¹³

Figure S19. *in situ* optical images of the SL-NiCo LDHs NSs/HOPG electrode. The images were acquired by the optical microscope vertically suspended on the EC-AFM setup. The microbubble appears and grows as the potential increases, while scanning in reverse or abruptly pausing the bias makes the microbubble gradually become smaller and finally disappear. With a constant voltage of 700 mV, the size of the microbubble expanded with the reaction time and eventually detached from the surface when it reached a sufficient size. The evolving tendency coincided well with the observed behavior of nanobubbles during operation.

Figure S20. (a) LSV curves of SL-NiCo LDHs NSs before and after 8000 CVs (without IR correction). AFM image of the electrode after 8000 CVs with a scan size of (b) 10 μm * 10 μm and (c) 3 μm * 3 μm (insert: height profiles along the white line in c), red triangles mark intact NSs.

Figure S21. (a) AFM images obtained after 2 CVs. (b) Height profiles of Figure 3a along the white dashed line in a. (c) Approach force-separation curves recorded on the labeled wrinkle points in a.

Figure S22. *in situ* AFM images with fully stacking SL-NiCo LDHs NSs (extracted from Figure S5). Color scale, -1~4 nm. The image size is 801 nm*801 nm.

Figure S23. *in situ* AFM images with partially stacking SL-NiCo LDHs NSs (extracted from Figure S5). Color scale, -1~3 nm. Scale bar, 200 nm.

Figure S24. AFM topography images of stacking SL-NiCo LDHs NSs (a) at OCV, (b) after performing 3 CVs from 0 mV to 700 mV and (c) after the chronopotentiometry measurement at 700 mV for 30 s. Color bar, -4~4 nm. Scale bar, 200 nm. (d) Phase image after performing 3 CVs. Color bar, -6.3~1.7°.

Here, the AFM images were obtained with AFM tapping mode, which allows for simultaneous acquisition of the topography and phase images. When the probe encounters different compositions with varying surface stiffness/softness and/or adhesion between the tip and surface, the phase signal changes, which allows for the identification of regions that possess different surface mechanical priorities.¹⁴ The network structure exhibits the same contrast as the flat region in the phase profile. Combining this with SEM-EDX indicates that the wrinkles are most likely composed of NiCo LDHs instead of other species.

Figure S25. *in situ* AFM images of (a) SL-NiCo LDHs and (b) PSL-NiCo LDHs NSs. Scale bar, 100 nm. Color bar, -0.3~10.2 nm. The surface root mean square (RMS, donated as Sq) roughness increases from 0.08 nm to 0.10 nm after plasma irradiation, indicating the formation of defective surfaces on the NSs.

Figure S26. *in situ* AFM images of a fresh PSL-NiCo LDHs/HOPG electrode at (a) OCV and (b) 700 mV.

Figure S27. The corresponding Tafel slopes obtained from Figure 5d.

Figure S28. (a) LSV curves of a PSL-NiCo LDHs electrode before and after 8000 CVs (without IR correction) (b) AFM image of the electrode after 8000 CVs. Color bar, -2~6 nm. Scale bar, 500 nm. (c) Height profile along the white line in b.

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